

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF BIOCONVERSION OF RENEWABLE RAW MATERIALS IN ETHANOL

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Abstract

The article discusses an innovative technology for the bioconversion of reducible raw materials into ethanol.

Keywords: bioconversion, raw materials, ethanol.

Introduction

The development of the agro-industrial complex of industrialized countries, which are significantly dependent on imports of energy and raw materials for the chemical industry, especially oil, in recent years is associated with the maximum possible reduction in oil imports by organizing energy production). Such products include ethanol (or bioethanol), biomethanol, bio-butanol, biohydrogen and others. The prefix "bio" indicates not only the raw materials used for production, but also is a characteristic of the technologies used (especially their impact on the environment).

Ukraine's transport sector is almost entirely dependent on imports of crude oil and / or refined products - gasoline and diesel fuel. In addition, the country's agricultural sector has a strong raw material base for growing grain, sugar beets and other plants, and the processing industry has the capacity and trained staff to convert them to bioethanol - the world's most common substitute for gasoline and diesel fuel.

The main economic criterion for assessing the prospects for mass use of bioethanol is its cost compared to the cost of mineral fuels. Approximately half of the cost of bioethanol is the cost of raw materials. Therefore, the use of the latest technologies and equipment both in agriculture and in enterprises producing bioethanol is necessary a condition for the development of the bioethanol market and the growing demand for it.

In addition, the so-called "Technical ethanol", ie ethanol intended for use as a raw material or component of the products of enterprises in many industries. Experience shows that in the vast majority of industries, oil as a raw material can be replaced by bioethanol and similar products made from renewable raw materials.

The most famous example is the production of synthetic rubber from ethanol according to the Lebedev method.

The full-scale use of ethanol for technical purposes is also directly related to its cost - whether it is competitive compared to the cost of minerals (a widely used term in world publications - fossils), which necessitates the use of advanced technological and technical solutions.

Given the capabilities of agriculture and the available capacity of distilleries today, the most promising for our country is the production of ethanol for various purposes from starchy raw materials, especially corn.

The biological conversion of the carbonaceous complex of corn (as well as other grains) into ethanol has several stages, including enzymatic conversion of raw polymers into mono- and di-carbohydrates, fermentation of fermented carbohydrates with yeast, separation of ethanol from aqueous solution and, if necessary, its from concomitant impurities.

The interconnectedness of these stages means that changes in technological parameters of one of them necessitate changes in technological parameters and methods of other stages, so it is necessary to analyze the consequences of implementing certain technological solutions for the whole ethanol production process and their impact on consumer properties. products.

1. Features of cultivation of industrial yeast in the conditions of introduction of thermoenzymatic processing of grain raw materials

New directions in the development of ethanol technology require increasing the concentration of dry matter of wort (DM), fermentation at elevated temper-

atures and concentrations of ethanol in the beer, ensuring further reduction of the cost of ethanol by saving raw materials and energy resources. In such conditions it is necessary to use highly productive breeds of yeast with increased osmophilicity, thermotolerance and fermentation activity.

Selection of physiologically active clones of ethanol yeast, technologically resistant to adverse factors that have increased productivity, osmophilicity and thermotolerance, can increase the efficiency of ethanol production by intensifying the processes of yeast generation and fermentation, reducing losses of ethanol and raw materials.

Thermotolerant yeast retains high fermentation activity when increasing the temperature of the nascent wort to 35... 38°C, which allows to significantly reduce water consumption for cooling fermentors. In addition, such yeasts have high osmophilicity, ie resistance to high concentrations of DM in wort (up to 27-32%), high concentrations of ethanol and related products of yeast in mature fermentation.

To obtain high quality ethanol, the biochemical activity of yeast is of great importance. Their physiological state affects the rate of biochemical processes and the composition of fermentation by-products. The physiological state of yeast largely depends on the chemical composition of the wort, which must contain sufficient amounts of germinals, minerals and vitamins. Taking into account all the features of the optimal living conditions of yeast, selecting the optimal composition of the substrate, you can get a product of the required quality at minimal cost.

In the process of yeast reproduction, the role of nitrogen nutrition increases, the need for which depends on the growth phase of yeast. In the exponential growth phase, the content of free intracellular amino acids in yeast is almost twice as high as their content in seed yeast. In addition to direct assimilation, biosynthesis of amino acids and proteins from inorganic nitrogen and organic carbon can occur in cells.

In the process of fermentation can be divided into two main periods, characterized by different states of yeast. In the induction period of fermentation, which coincides with the logarithmic phase on the yeast growth curve, there is an intensive accumulation of yeast biomass at a relatively low rate of consumption of carbohydrate substrate and a higher rate of utilization of nitrogen nutrition. Upon reaching the stationary phase on the yeast growth curve and the accumulation of a certain concentration, a period of intensive fermentation begins at a low rate of yeast reproduction.

The need of yeast for nitrogen nutrition is mainly related to protein synthesis during their reproduction and the active action of enzyme complexes that maintain the required level of energy metabolism in the utilization of carbohydrate components.

In recent years, there have been significant changes in ethanol production technology. Malt is completely replaced by concentrated enzyme preparations of selective action. The use of purified amylolytic drugs at the stage of saccharification leads to insufficient accumulation in the wort of amino acids that are necessary for yeast in the process of their reproduction,

which adversely affects the physiological activity of yeast.

It was found that the growth of yeast in the wort with high concentrations of DM is limited by nitrogen nutrition. As the wort concentration increases, the degree of influence of nitrogen nutrition on the process of yeast reproduction and fermentation process increases. The use of grain wort enriched with amine nitrogen as a result of proteolysis of plant proteins of raw materials increases the fermentation activity of yeast, their osmophilicity and tolerance to ethanol. At the same time, excessive enrichment of the fermented wort with amine nitrogen can lead to the accumulation in the mature wort of yeast by-products. Therefore, it is advisable to enrich the yeast wort with nitrogen to ensure active reproduction of yeast at the stage of yeast generation.

The total yeast need for nitrogen is 20... 25 mg per 10 billion cells. Active reproduction of yeast is observed at a concentration of amine nitrogen of 35 mg / dm³ of wort. Ammonia water, ammonium salts and urea are used as nitrogenous food. Some publications have reported that excessive amounts of urea in the nutrient medium may lead to the formation of ethyl carbamate, which has carcinogenic effects.

In addition to organic sources of nitrogen at the stage of yeast generation, it is advisable to specify a protease for the hydrolysis of proteins to amino acids. The amount of protease is determined in each case depending on the raw materials and technological decisions made at the enterprise.

It was found that changes in the metabolism of yeast cells cultured on wort treated with proteolytic enzyme preparations (EP), which include the enzymes proteinase and peptidase, are accompanied by decreased biosynthesis of metabolic by-products: aldehydes, higher alcohols and organic acids. Yeast, which is cultivated on a wort enriched with amino acids, has increased osmophilicity and tolerance to fermentation products.

With the transition of ethanol technology to low-temperature regimes of hydroenzymatic processing of grain raw materials with the use of concentrated enzyme preparations, there is a need to improve the technology of production of yeast. According to the results of scientific research and production tests, an improved technology for the production of yeast is proposed, which differs from the traditional composition of the nutrient medium and the duration of fermentation.

The physiological activity of yeast is influenced not only by nitrogenous substances, but also by phosphorus nutrition and vitamins. This is especially true when replacing malt with enzyme preparations that do not contain the necessary growth substances for alcoholic yeast.

The presence of sufficient amounts of mineral nitrogen and phosphorus in the environment cannot completely replace such a complex source of nitrogen, phosphorus and growth substances, which is malt milk. Therefore, in the study of conditions that increase the efficiency of fermentation of sugar wort, corn extract was proposed as a source of growth substances.

The introduction of corn extract at the stage of yeast cultivation increases the rate of fermentation of

carbons from the beginning to the end of the process. The amount of carbon dioxide in experiments using corn extract for the fourth hour of fermentation is 32... 35 percent higher than in the control. With increasing duration of fermentation, the difference in the formation of carbon dioxide in the experiment and in the control decreased and at 48 hours was approximately 5 percent. The total duration of fermentation is reduced from 72 to 48 hours. When using corn extract increases the physiological activity of yeast, achieves a more complete assimilation of carbons and increases the yield of ethanol. For example, the content of ethanol-soluble carbons, which characterizes the fermentation

activity of yeast, in the experiment was 16 percent lower than in the control.

Analysis of the content of metabolic by-products showed that the increase in ethanol yield is also achieved by reducing the amount of glycerol, aldehydes, acids and esters, the amount of which in the experiment was significantly less than in the control (table 1). It can be assumed that in the absence of limitation of physiological activity of yeast by environmental components such as nitrogen, phosphorus, amino acids and other growth factors of yeast, a complex source of which is corn extract, changes the direction of ethanol fermentation and reduces carbon costs for secondary synthesis.

Table 1

The effect of corn extract on the performance of beer

	Urea + orthophosphoric acid	Urea + orthophosphoric acid + corn extract
Acidity, deg.	0,40	0,39
PH	4,54	4,59
Visible concentration of DM,%	0,2	0,1
The actual concentration of DM,%	2,9	3,0
Unfermented carbon compounds, g / 100 cm ³ , incl.	0,272	0,231
Soluble carbon compounds	0,256	0,200
Undissolved starch	0,011	0,018
Alcohol-soluble carbon compounds	0,230	0,193
Dextrins	0,023	0,006
The concentration of ethanol,% vol.	6,6	6,7
The yield of ethanol, dal / t of fermented solution	64,8	66,3
Glycerin content, g / 100 cm ³	1,063	0,769
Aldehyde content. % vol	0,0024	0,0012
The content of higher alcohols,% vol	0,106	0,134
Volatile acid content, mg / dm ³	850,4	562,5
The content of esters, mg / dm ³	2355,9	1760,0

In the practical application of thermo-enzymatic treatment of raw materials, a number of distilleries use technological regimes that provide an average duration of treatment of the mixture with α -amylase 3 hours and saccharification of dilute starch for 45... 60 minutes. At such modes 25... 30% of nucleating carbon compounds

are formed. When cultivating yeast on such a wort, it is necessary to determine their physiological activity by separating part of the mature yeast (10... 12%) from the previous cycle to use them as seed yeast in the next cycle (table 2).

Table 2

Characteristics of sowing yeast depending on the number of reseedings

Indicators	Number of reseedings			
	1	2	3	4
pH of the medium	3,7	3,8	3,9	3,7
Acidity, deg	0,82	0,75	0,70	0,50
Visible concentration of DM,%	3,2	4,8	5,6	10,8
The actual concentration of DM,%	5,5	5,6	6,2	11,6
The concentration of ethanol,% vol.	6,65	6,45	5,25	3,85
Unfermented carbon compounds, g / 100 cm ³	1,75	1,98	2,81	5,57
Number of yeast cells, million / cm ³	125	98	84	78

With an increase in the number of yeast transplants from the previous to the next technological cycle, all indicators of mature yeast deteriorate. The use of such yeast at the anaerobic stage has shown that from cycle to cycle increases the duration of fermentation - from 72 to 94 hours, increases losses with unfermented carbon compounds and thereby significantly reduces

the yield of ethanol. Analysis of the carbon composition of mature mash shows that the main losses of carbons are caused by the increased content of ethanol-soluble compounds of carbon and dextrins. Insufficient hydrolysis of starch at the stage of thermoformative treatment of raw materials leads to a decrease in the physiological activity of yeast does not allow to fully

realize the benefits of thermoenzymatic dissolution and hydrolysis of starch. Low fermentation energy of yeast is due to limiting their reproduction by sources of organic nitrogen, phosphorus and growth factors.

These shortcomings are eliminated in the developed technological mode of preparation of the environment for the cultivation of yeast. Its essence is. That sugary wort intended for use in the preparation of industrial yeast is further dextrinized and saccharified. Additional application of thermostable amylase in the amount of 1.0-1.2 units of activity per 1 g of starch provides for 50... 60 minutes. The degree of dextrinization at the level of 98... 99.7%, and additional application of glucoamylase in the amount of 1.5-2.0 units of activity per 1 g of starch ensures the achievement of the ratio of glucose: dextrans - 3.5: 1. Yeast grown on wort with additional saccharification is characterized by a higher specific rate of reproduction, fermentation energy and productivity.

When cultivating yeast on wort after additional saccharification, losses with unfermented carbons are reduced, primarily due to ethanol-soluble carbon compounds. The amount of ethanol synthesized by yeast on wort with additional saccharification exceeds the same figure compared to yeast on wort without additional saccharification, by 2.2... 2.3% relative.

The introduction of corn extract into the environment provides the necessary and sufficient levels of organic nitrogen and phosphorus, primarily consumed by yeast, and helps to increase the specific rate of their growth. In addition, amino acids and vitamins are added with corn extract, which reduces the loss of carbohydrates for the synthesis of yeast biomass.

The set of proposed technological methods and parameters optimizes the composition of the nutrient medium in the ratio of carbon: nitrogen: phosphorus and glucose: dextrans and thus increase the productivity of yeast for ethanol biosynthesis and reduce costs with unfermented carbohydrates.

These data can be the basis for the development of the optimal technological regime for the cultivation of seed yeast and fermentation of wort obtained by thermoenzymatic treatment of grain raw materials.

In the production of ethanol, the existing and promising opportunities to change the biochemical composition of the nutrient medium for yeast with the help of corrective drugs open the way to significantly improve fermentation rates, including the yield of the target product, fermentation rate. The yield of by-products of fermentation, organoleptic characteristics of marketable products (if necessary), as well as increasing the protein value after alcohol bard.

The market offers ethanol producers various complexes of biologically active substances (vitamins, minerals, amino acids, etc.). The use of which improves the technological properties of alcoholic yeast. The feasibility of using biologically active additives at the stage of sowing yeast cultivation is decided in each case primarily in the light of economic feasibility.

Another area of intensification of production yeast technology is their aerobic cultivation.

Traditional cultivation of seed yeast in the processing of carbohydrate raw materials into ethanol is

carried out under anaerobic conditions at relatively low growth rates and high specific consumption of the substrate. The result is a production yeast with a cell concentration of 100... 120 million / ml. This technology requires significant volumes of yeast generators, increased length of food communications and, accordingly, increased costs for their washing and sterilization.

Aerobic cultivation of alcoholic yeast allows you to grow the required amount of yeast biomass in a shorter time and with lower raw material costs.

According to the results of experimental studies, the optimal conditions for the cultivation of seed yeast under aerobic conditions were determined.

At the beginning of the cultivation process, air consumption is $18 \text{ m}^3 / \text{m}^3 \cdot \text{h}$ with an increase to $60 \text{ m}^3 / \text{m}^3 \cdot \text{h}$; the speed of mixing in the middle and at the end of the process is one and a half to two times higher than at the beginning. The cultivation temperature that is optimal for yeast respiration is 30... 32°C. The initial concentration of DM wort 12... 15%. Aerobic cultivation provides an increase in yeast biomass by 2... 3 times. Reducing the concentration of carbon compounds in the wort directs the process of biosynthesis in the direction of biomass accumulation, rather than increasing the formation of bioassimilation products.

To restructure the enzyme systems of yeast cells for efficient fermentation of carbohydrates in ethanol at the end of yeast generation, the yeast is kept under anaerobic conditions for 3... 4 hours.

Under aerobic conditions, yeast cultivation emits much more heat than anaerobic ones, which necessitates measures to cool the nutrient medium.

Air supply devices must ensure uniform and efficient dispersion in the yeast.

Practice shows that the suction communication of the compressor should be as high as possible above the ground. The air is cleaned with mechanical filters (removal of coarse impurities) and filters that remove microorganisms (such as "Laik").

2. Innovative technologies of alcohol fermentation in the production of ethanol from grain

Periodic fermentation is used in domestic grain ethanol production enterprises. It ensures compliance with the necessary aseptic conditions of alcohol fermentation and the ability to adjust at all stages of fermentation, but requires large geometric volumes of fermentation battery and is economically feasible at a daily capacity of 4.5... 6.0 thousand decalitres of ethanol. This method should be used only in enterprises that produce ethanol for the needs of the food industry and medicine. More efficient methods of fermentation of grain raw materials need to be used in enterprises with higher daily capacity that produce bioethanol as fuel and for technical needs.

Other methods of fermentation are described - cyclic, flow-recirculation and continuous-flow, which due to the development of pathogenic microflora (and the corresponding fermentation of the mash), as well as the impossibility of adjustment are not implemented in the production of ethanol from grain, although ethanol from molasses using continuous fermentation.

The capacity of the fermentation compartment can be increased primarily by increasing the concentration of ethanol in the mature mash, which is directly proportional to the increase in the concentration of the wort. During the fermentation of wort from starch-containing raw materials, the process of hydrolysis of starch continues in the fermentation process, which determines its duration. High concentrations of ethanol inhibit the activity of yeast. Therefore, along with the use of osmophilic yeast strains, it is important to ensure deeper hydrolysis of polycarbohydrogens of the wort before fermentation. This can be achieved by increasing the dosage of enzyme preparations by 25... 35%.

Along with this, the increase in the degree of hydrolysis can also be achieved by extending the time of action of glucoamylase under optimal conditions of its action: pH = 4.7... 5.5, temperature 55... 57°C. studies, including in production conditions, show that extending the saccharification time to 3... 5 hours increases the degree of hydrolysis of starch from 60... 70% to 85... 90%, and in some cases more.

Effective fermentation of highly concentrated wort is achieved by increasing the productivity of the yeast population, which accelerates the fermentation process both at its initial stage and in general. Taking into account the fact that the yeast of domestic enterprises can withstand the ethanol content within 11.0... 12.0% vol., The concentrated wort is diluted with bard filtrate cooled to a temperature of 25... 30°C. The required amount of stillage filtrate is calculated taking into account the reduction of the initial concentration of DM to 22... 24%.

For the cultivation of sowing and industrial yeast it is necessary to prepare a wort from good quality raw materials with a concentration of 18... 19% DM and a high degree of hydrolysis of starch.

Fermentation of concentrated wort can be carried out according to a continuous scheme with recirculation, which ensures maximum use of yeast productivity. The steady flow of this process is ensured by setting the rate of dilution of the nutrient medium $D = 0.1... 0.125 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

Effective fermentation of concentrated wort can be carried out periodically. The main disadvantage is the slowdown of the initial fermentation rate for the period of the lag phase (12... 14 hours), which takes place in each fermentation apparatus after the start of its filling. The main reason is the low initial concentration of yeast biomass and the inhibition of its growth by high concentrations of carbohydrates.

The lag phase can be eliminated by sequentially filling the fermentors with a mixture of candied wort and actively fermenting wort (50/50 ratio). For this purpose, a fermentation mode is proposed, in which two battery fermentors (so-called main fermentators), connected in series at the bottom by a flow line and bound by a flow circuit, operate in continuous yeast-main fermentation mode, and the rest of the fermentation devices (9 pieces) work in periodic mode.

Yeast production yeast is sent to the pre-washed and disinfected (steamed) first main fermenter in the amount of 50% of its volume with simultaneous supply of concentrated sugar wort and bard filtrate. The speed

of feeding the mixture "wort / filtrate bard" is maintained at 10... 12% of the volume of the fermenter for 1 hour. The concentration of yeast biomass in the main fermentation apparatus of the battery is at the level of 100 million / ml.

After filling the first main fermentation apparatus, the flow to the second main apparatus is opened, while the wort and filtrate of the bard continue to flow to the first fermentation apparatus with simultaneous filling of the second through the overflow line. The wort is continuously removed from the second main fermentation apparatus, which actively ferments and mixes with the candied wort. Part of the mixed stream is diverted to the first main apparatus to support the yeast generation and fermentation process, and the other part of the flow is successively filled with fermentation machines operating periodically, from which beer is pumped out after the fermentation process.

The ethanol accumulated during fermentation gradually leads to energy starvation of cells, cessation of their growth and biosynthesis of ethanol, and as a final result - to the death of yeast cells. The process of inhibition of vital activity and death of yeast begins to manifest itself at ethanol concentrations in the environment from 6... 8% to 10... 12% depending on the osmophilicity of the strain and is accompanied by a number of metabolic changes leading to ethanol contamination by side metabolites.

In the production of ethanol from starchy raw materials, the process of hydrolysis of starch and its components continues throughout the fermentation time. Continuous fermentation requires deeper hydrolysis of biopolymers of raw materials before fermentation than during periodic fermentation. This is ensured by the intensification of the process of thermoenzymatic processing of raw materials, in particular by increasing the period of saccharification under optimal conditions of action of enzyme preparations, as well as increasing the concentration of yeast biomass.

3. Measures to ensure microbiological purity in the technology of ethanol from starch-containing raw materials

Bacterial infection of the environment is one of the main problems in the production of ethanol, negatively affecting all stages of the technological process. Uncontrolled reproduction of pathogenic microorganisms can stop or severely delay the growth and metabolic activity of yeast. Bacteria are the last competitors for food sources. Deficiency of carbohydrogen leads to a decrease in ethanol yield. Many bacteria produce organic acids and other substances that impair the reproductive properties of yeast, inactivate the amylolytic enzymes of the wort. Bacterial contamination results in an increase in the concentration of by-products that impair the organoleptic properties of ethanol.

Pathogenic microorganisms. Occurring in the production of ethanol, belong to several groups. One of the constant contaminants of ethanol fermentation are members of the genus *Lactobacillus*, which produce lactic acid as the main product of their metabolism. To combat foreign microflora, domestic companies widely use chemical antiseptics: formalin, chlorinated lime and caustic soda. But their use increases the amount of

aldehydes and some other undesirable compounds in ethanol, which degrades the quality of marketable products. Due to this, new effective and safe antibacterial drugs are constantly being sought.

The use of high (135... 155°C) temperatures in water-heat treatment provided partial disinfection of grain. The transition to heat-enzymatic treatment at low temperatures has exacerbated the issue of counteracting the infection of wort by foreign microorganisms.

It should be noted that the task is not to completely destroy foreign microorganisms. Their vegetative forms died at high temperatures, and spores remained in the incubation state and when exposed to a favorable environment (wort in the saccharifier) began active life and reproduction. Therefore, the problem of control of foreign microflora is solved by creating such conditions in substrates (batch, diluted mass, wort), in which foreign microorganisms do not multiply or multiply minimally. It is impossible to ensure the complete absence of foreign microorganisms and therefore it is only a matter of conditionally sterile conduct of the process during thermoenzymatic treatment.

The main sources of microorganisms in ethanol plants - raw materials, water, air and auxiliary materials.

Microorganisms develop in all parts of the technological line at temperatures up to 75°C. During water-heat treatment of grain raw materials, especially at the stage of preparation of grain mixture at a temperature of 60... 70°C, the number of microorganisms increases sharply, which reduces the pH of the wort and adversely affects the bacterial thermostable α -amylase. The result is an increase in the loss of raw starch.

Metabolites released by microorganisms create certain difficulties at the stage of fermentation. The greatest danger is posed by mucus-forming and thermophilic bacteria.

Mucus-forming lactic acid bacteria (*Leuconostoc mesenteroides*, *Leuconostoc dextranicum*) form a gem-like capsule around themselves, which allows them to withstand high (up to 90°C) temperatures. *Leuconostoc* colonies cover the surface of equipment and pipelines with mucus, which is difficult to wash off with water, so mechanical and chemical treatment is required. As an example - 1 million embryos *Leuconostoc* is able to decompose up to 0.6% of nascent carbohydrates in 1 hour.

At temperatures of 60... 70°C there is an active development of mesophilic putrefactive and butyric acid bacteria. Putrefactive bacteria destroy grain proteins with the formation of ammonia, acetone, organic acids, acetaldehyde and other harmful metabolites.

Butyric acid bacteria hydrolyze pectin, starch and ferment carbohydrates with the formation of butyric and acetic acids, acetone and various alcohols.

Most thermophiles have an optimal temperature of 50... 70°C, and some thermophiles metabolism continues at temperatures 78... 85°C, so when choosing temperature regimes must take into account the development of infectious microflora to ensure that at the stage of thermoenzymatic processing of raw materials not only achieve maximum dissolution of starch, but also to provide suppression of foreign microorganisms.

To effectively combat contaminating microflora, it is necessary to select an antiseptic that has a wide range of antimicrobial action with minimal adverse effects on yeast cells.

All antiseptics are characterized by toxicity to bacterial cells, which depends on the concentration of the drug and occurs only when antiseptics bind to microbial cells.

In recent years, the attention of domestic and foreign researchers has been drawn to antimicrobial drugs based on the guanide group. One such drug is Aquaton-10, which is a 25% solution of a biocidal polymer compound that is non-toxic to warm-blooded organisms and is used in drinking water treatment technology.

Another drug - Vazin - is used to antisept the nutrient medium of the seed culture of feed yeast. It is an aqueous solution of 1.3.5-tri (β -hydroxyethyl) hexahydro-5-triazine with additives. The content of the main substance 45... 51%.

Antibiotics Freecont and Distiferm RG are used for antiseptic intermediates in the brewing industry and other food industries and are promising for use in ethanol production.

Studies of asepting preparations on wort from starch-containing raw materials, which were obtained by heat-enzymatic treatment using concentrated enzyme preparations, were carried out. The wort was fermented with a thermotolerant strain of yeast race K-81 at a temperature of 32... 33°C.

To ensure model infection of the wort, a pure culture of the association of lactic acid bacteria, which was isolated from acidic mash, was used.

The effect of different concentrations of antiseptics on the yeast population and lactic acid bacteria was studied, in particular Aquaton-10 within 1... 100 ml / m³, Vazina - 0.25... 2.0 l / m³, Freent - 0.5... 1.5 g / m³, Distyferma RG - 0.25... 0.750 g / m³. Samples without antiseptic and with antiseptic formalin were used as controls.

The research results are shown in table 3.

As a result, the optimal doses of antiseptics were determined: for Aquaton-10 - 100 ml / m³, Vazina - 0.5 l / m³, Distyferma RG - 0.50 g / m³ and for Freecont - 1.0... 1.5 g / m³. At certain costs, high fermentation activity of yeast is provided, and the increase in acidity of the wort infected with lactic acid bacteria does not exceed 0.50... 0.55 1N. NaOH per 20 cm³ of brew, while in the control sample it increased by 2.0... 2.4 times.

The effect of the studied drugs and their costs were tested on non-sterile wort from starch-containing raw materials.

The acidity of mature brews when using antimicrobial drugs Aquaton-10, Vazin, Frikont and Distiferm RG did not exceed 0.45... 0.54 ml 1 n. NaOH per 20 cm³ of brew. With the use of formalin there was an increase in acidity by 10... 16% compared with the studied antiseptics.

The obtained data confirm the antiseptic effect of the studied drugs and the compliance of the selected concentrations with the condition to ensure the prevention of effects on the fermentation activity of yeast.

Table 3

The effect of antiseptic concentration on the increase in the acidity of the beer

№	Preparation	Concentration	Amount	Acidity, ml 1 N. NaOH per 20 cm ³ of beer		
				For 1 day	For 2 day	For 3 day
1	Aquaton-10	ml/M ³	0,00	0,60	0,92	1,30
			100	0,30	0,38	0,48
			50	0,30	0,42	0,50
			20	0,32	0,44	0,50
			5	0,32	0,48	0,52
			3	0,38	0,55	0,60
			1	0,56	0,70	0,85
2	Vazin	l/M ³	0,00	0,38	0,94	1,32
			2,0	0,17	0,18	0,18
			1,0	0,21	0,22	0,48
			0,50	0,26	0,28	0,50
			0,25	0,25	0,30	0,65
3	Distiform RG	g/M ³	0,00	0,44	0,90	1,02
			0,75	0,20	0,45	0,50
			0,50	0,24	0,48	0,52
			0,25	0,34	0,58	0,64
4	Frikont	g/M ³	0,00	0,45	0,85	1,10
			1,5	0,25	0,35	0,45
			1,0	0,27	0,40	0,50
			0,5	0,27	0,45	0,60

Analysis of the carbohydrate composition of mature mash showed that when using the studied drugs, the content of soluble carbohydrates is reduced by 4...14% compared with the control. Undissolved starch in beer does not change significantly. This can be explained by the fact that the studied drugs do not affect the activity of enzymes during saccharification and before saccharification of the wort during fermentation.

In the process of wort fermentation with the use of antiseptics, the intensity of carbon-hydrogen and nitrogen metabolism in the yeast cell changes, which is directly related to the biosynthesis of organic ethanol impurities.

Conclusion

The use of ethanol in the world is carried out in three main ways. The first (and main in the amount of ethanol) is its use as a renewable liquid fuel (or additive) in internal combustion engines. The second area of application of ethanol is its use as a raw material for industrial processing and a component of industrial products. The third, traditional for Ukraine direction is the use of ethanol for the needs of the food industry

(primarily for the production of alcoholic beverages), the needs of medicine (both in the production of medicines and as a disinfectant) and perfume industry.

In the first two cases, ethanol competes on the market with similar products of mineral origin: oil and refined products, natural gas and so on. A crucial condition for the large-scale use of ethanol is to bring its value closer to the value of mineral analogues.

Therefore, the introduction of innovative technologies in ethanol production - increasing the concentration of ethanol in mature malt, reducing the temperature of enzymatic processing of grain, finding new raw materials and microorganisms-producers, reducing energy consumption is a key condition for successful development of ethanol industry. for industry. This increases the resource and energy independence of the state, creates preconditions for increasing exports of agro-industrial complex (and hence its investment attractiveness and innovative development), which generally has a positive impact on the economic and political state of our state.